

STUDY ON IN SITU REACTION-PROCESSED AL (ZN, CU)-AL₂O₃ (ZNO, CUO)
PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *metal matrix composites; particulate; in-situ; zinc oxide; alumina particle*

Abstract

Particle reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) are an important class of composite materials. During last decades, particulate metal matrix composites have found special industrial applications in producing wear-resistance components. One of the best ways for producing cast particulate composites is In-Situ methods. The advantage is considered to be of higher compatibility and improved particle matrix interfaces. A commonly adopted in situ method involves reaction between a metal oxide and aluminum to produce alumina particles or whisker reinforcements. By completing the alumina formation reaction, the reduced metal usually further reacts with Al to form intermetallic phases, which also act as reinforcements in the matrix of the composite. Because of the formation of ultrafine and stable ceramic reinforcements, the in situ MMCs are found to exhibit excellent mechanical properties. In this study, In-situ particle-reinforced aluminum based cast composites have been synthesized by dispersion of externally added Zinc Oxide particles into molten aluminum at different processing temperatures. Alumina particles (Al₂O₃) form through chemical reaction of ZnO particles with molten aluminum. Simultaneously, the chemical reaction also releases Zinc, which dissolves into molten aluminum during solidification. X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy have been used to study the various reaction mechanisms and transformations.

Keywords: metal matrix composites; particulate; in-situ; zinc oxide; alumina particle

Introduction

Aluminum metal matrix composites (Al/MMCs) are considered as a group of advanced materials for their light weight, high strength, high specific modulus, low thermal expansion coefficient, and their good wear resistance properties[1,2,3]. Aluminum-alumina particle composites have great technological interests due to their improved mechanical properties as compared to unreinforced alloys [4]. Basically, aluminum can be used to reduce most metallic oxides. Therefore, all metallic oxides which are thermodynamically less stable than alumina, could be used in In-situ method. A typical reduction reaction of a metallic oxide in aluminum melt can be written as :

The higher the free energy difference between metallic oxide and alumina, the easier the reduction reaction with aluminum with higher turbulence and heat generation. The reduction reaction for CuO can be written as:

In some cases it is possible to remove the Me from the melt and reach exceeded amount of alumina particles to the matrix. A good candidate for this purpose is zinc oxide because of low boiling temperature of zinc. If zinc oxide (ZnO) is utilized instead of copper oxide in order to oxidize aluminum, the reduction reaction will be as:

In other words, energetically molten aluminum reduces CuO easier than ZnO and the reaction temperature for aluminum with ZnO is higher than aluminum with CuO. Several researchers have used zinc oxide as the metallic oxide for the aluminothermic reaction to produce in-situ Al/Al₂O₃ composites [5,6,7]. No successful attempt has been reported in the literature to synthesize in-situ alumina reinforcement using liquid state methods. For example, Kobashi and Choh[8] reported that when zinc oxide powder was added to a vortex of molten aluminum, no chemical reaction occurred [8]. This could be attributed to very poor wettability of zinc oxide particles by molten aluminum.

The main objective of the present work is reduction of zinc oxide and copper oxide in liquid aluminum in order to produce in situ aluminum–alumina composite.

Experimental procedure

Commercially pure aluminum powder (99.7% purity, Khorasan PM Co., IRAN) with a particle size of < 62 μm and pure zinc oxide powder (> 99.9% purity, Merck, Germany) with particle size of less than 0.5 μm and copper oxide with particle size of less than 0.5 μm were used as raw materials. Mixtures of aluminum and zinc oxide powder with stoichiometric ratio of their aluminothermic reaction (2Al + 3ZnO = Al₂O₃ + 3Zn) were milled in a planetary ball mill machine (Retsch PM100) using hardened chromium steel vial and balls under argon atmosphere for 40, 60, 80, and 100 min. A ball-to-powder mass ratio of 10 and rotation speed of 350 rpm was employed. A Philips diffractometer (40 kV) with Cu Kα radiation (λ = 0.15406 nm) was used for XRD tests. The milled powder mixture and cast samples were observed by Seron ALS-2100 scanning electron microscope.

Pure aluminum was melted in alumina crucible and superheated to 775 °C for thermal homogeneity. In order to spread oxide mixes, to the molten aluminum matrix the liquid was stirred by a spiral blade surface-coated graphite impeller. At the same time, each activated powder (10wt%ZnO, 10wt%ZnO-5wt%CuO) was gradually injected to the melt using a patented injection gun (Iranian patent 42,117) and argon as the carrier gas [9]. Stirring started by oxide addition to the melt and ended by completion of reaction. All specimens were cast at 750 °C in metallic mold while argon inert gas was being blown on top of the mold during pouring and casting periods.

Results and discussions

Figure 1 shows the SEM micrographs of the powder mixture activated for different times. SEM investigations revealed a significant reduction in the size of the aluminum particles by milling [10]. Furthermore, after 40 min of milling, aluminum particles were all covered with a layer of zinc. As seen, there are still some non-interacting zinc oxide particles left. When milling time was increased to 60 min, not only the aluminum particles were indented more by the zinc oxide particles, but also the number of non-interacting zinc oxide particles decreased as well [9].

Figure 1: SEM micrographs of the powder mixture (Al-80wt% ZnO) activated for 40, 60, 80 and 100 min

Figure 2 shows the X-ray diffractograms of the powders activated for different times. After 40 minutes of ball milling, the peak positions still matched those of raw material. A new peak appeared, when ball milling was continued up to 60 minutes. The new peak, which matched that of zinc, indicated the start of the reaction. Because the alumina that forms at low temperature is amorphous, [2,3] no alumina peak is seen in Figure 2. According to X-ray diffractograms, 40 minutes is the time that causes maximum activation of the powders without any reaction.

Figure 2: X-Ray patterns of activated powder for 40, 60, 80 and 100 minutes

Specimens for SEM observations were taken from the as-cast materials and prepared conventionally. Finally, all specimens were polished by MgO powders and were washed with liquid acetone in ultrasonic apparatus for 10 min. The specimens were observed on Seron ALS-2100 scanning electron microscope .

In SEM micrographs, distribution of white particles in matrix is seen. Fig.3 shows some in situ formed alumina particles. They are sized from 1 to 2 μ m as biggest and some spread smaller particles. Fig3-a shows the SEM micrographs of alumina particles obtained from Al reactions with 10wt%ZnO and Fig3-b shows the SEM micrographs of alumina particles obtained from Al reaction with a mixture of CuO-ZnO. As seen, a desirable distribution of white alumina particles exists in both cases. Comparing the micrographs of Fig3-a and Fig3-b, it is seen that the amount of alumina particle in Fig3-b are more than Fig3-a. Regarding particles in Fig3-a created from Zinc oxide solely and in Fig3-b created from the copper oxide and zinc oxide mixture, it is concluded that the amount of alumina obtained from mixture of zinc oxide and copper oxide is more than those obtained from copper oxide or zinc oxide individually. The reason could be for higher oxidation reaction and higher turbulency of aluminum with copper oxide compared to zinc oxide. These results are in good agreement with those presented by Kobashi and Choh works [11]. Further investigation to control the particles' size and dispersion by changing the composition of mixture needs to be addressed.

(a) Al-10wt% ZnO

(b) Al-10wt% ZnO-5wt% CuO

Figure 3: micrographs of the reinforcement particles formed and distributed in the matrix

Thermodynamically, according to reaction (2),(3) aluminum element reduces zinc oxide and copper oxide and produces zinc and copper element and aluminum oxide (alumina).

Since the difference between free energies of alumina and copper oxides is significantly higher than that of zinc oxide, the copper oxide was reduced easily and made the condition easier to reduce the zinc oxide.

It is concluded that in these mixes, copper oxide plays two different roles, firstly as a physical separator for zinc oxide and secondly it performs reduction reaction with liquid aluminum easily and supplies the heat necessary for starting reduction reaction of zinc oxide with liquid aluminum. In other words, reduction reaction of copper oxide plays a catalytic role for zinc oxide reduction.

The in situ formed particles will act as strengthener (second phase) and a composite material is obtained. Thus, the amount of formed particles in this in situ method depends on the reduction reactions of CuO and ZnO in the melt. Therefore, the elemental copper and zinc concentrations in the matrix could introduce the amount of alumina particles produced as strengthener material for the composite.

Conclusions

- 1.The in situ fabrication of aluminum–alumina composites with zinc oxide was done.
2. Direct reduction of ZnO by aluminum can be realized by activating the ZnO and aluminum powder mixture prior to its addition to the superheated melt.
3. Milling for 40 minutes leads to optimum activation of the reactant powders (ZnO and Al). Such an activation leads to a decrease in the reaction temperature.
- 4.It was necessary to mix zinc oxide with copper oxide powders to increase the amount of alumina in the matrix. Furthermore, CuO in the mixture mostly played a reaction starter role, violation and energy supplier for reduction reaction of molten aluminum with ZnO. SEM observations showed that the amount of alumina particles obtained from mixture of zinc oxide and copper oxide were more than those obtained from copper oxide or zinc oxide individually.

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